

AFRICA'S SPACE INDUSTRY VALUE CHAIN

and the

AFRICA'S SPACE IDENTITY
Natasha van Rooyen

Wicked problems in the African space industry and their relation to SDGs

The African space industry holds several complex interconnected social, economic, and environmental challenges. These issues occur at both national and continental levels, aligning to the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Author:

Natasha van Rooyen

As part of an assessment paper: *Sustainability Development Goals and the Law*.

Under the program: *Democratising Education for Global Sustainability and Justice*.

September 2024

University of Cambridge

Lucy Cavendish College

Hughes Hall

1. LIMITED FUNDING AND INVESTMENT

Many African countries lack significant government funding and private investment for space programs, which limits innovation and capacity-building in the space sector.

- **Related SDGs:**

SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth

Underinvestment in space infrastructure limits job creation and economic development.

SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure

There is a need for sustainable industrial growth and innovation to drive advancements in space technology.

2. LACK OF SKILLED WORKFORCE

There is a shortage of skilled professionals and expertise in space sciences, engineering, and policy, leading to a reliance on external support or expatriate talent.

- **Related SDGs:**

SDG 4: Quality Education

The shortage of technical education and specialized training programs hinders capacity building in the space sector.

SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth

A lack of skilled personnel limits the potential for local employment in high-tech fields.

3. FRAGMENTATION IN SPACE POLICY AND GOVERNANCE

Many African countries operate in isolation, lacking coordinated space policies, regulations, or collaborative frameworks, leading to fragmented efforts and inefficiency at both national and continental levels.

- **Related SDGs:**

SDG 16: Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions

Developing strong institutions, laws, and policies at national and regional levels is essential for effective governance of the space industry.

4. ENVIRONMENTAL AND CLIMATE VULNERABILITY

Africa is highly vulnerable to the effects of climate change, and its space industry must address environmental challenges while remaining sustainable in its own activities.

- **Related SDGs:**

SDG 13: Climate Action

The space sector can contribute to climate monitoring and early warning systems, but environmental sustainability must be integrated into space initiatives.

SDG 15: Life on Land

Space technologies can support the preservation of terrestrial ecosystems by aiding environmental monitoring.

5. DIGITAL DIVIDE AND LIMITED ACCESS TO SPACE TECHNOLOGY

Unequal access to space technologies (e.g., satellite internet, earth observation) exacerbates the digital divide, especially in rural and underserved communities.

- **Related SDGs:**

SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure

Access to space-based technologies can drive digital inclusion, particularly in remote areas.

SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities

Space-based technologies can help bridge inequality gaps, providing infrastructure for marginalized and underserved populations.

6. SOVEREIGNTY AND EXTERNAL DEPENDENCE

Africa's space industry is often dependent on international collaborations for technology, resources, and expertise, which can compromise national sovereignty over space assets and data.

- **Related SDGs:**

SDG 17: Partnerships for the Goals – While international collaboration is crucial, there needs to be a focus on fostering more self-reliance and reducing dependency on external actors.

7. LIMITED AWARENESS AND PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT

Public understanding of space's potential contributions to economic growth, environmental sustainability, and scientific advancement is limited in Africa, which affects political will and private sector interest.

- **Related SDGs:**

SDG 4: Quality Education

Increased educational efforts are required to build awareness of space science and its benefits.

SDG 16: Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions

Public participation and engagement in space policy-making processes are critical for inclusive decision-making.

8. SPACE DEBRIS AND SUSTAINABLE USE OF OUTER SPACE

As Africa begins to launch more satellites and engage in space activities, managing space debris and ensuring the sustainable use of outer space will be crucial to avoid contributing to global environmental problems.

- **Related SDGs:**

SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production

Sustainable management of resources extends to space technologies, ensuring that space exploration does not contribute to space debris.

SDG 13: Climate Action

Space technologies can be part of the solution in monitoring and mitigating environmental challenges, including space debris.

Space is not an abstract frontier but an integral part of securing Africa's future, especially through the lens of sustainable development. Space technologies such as satellite communications, earth observation, and climate monitoring are crucial tools in addressing some of Africa's most pressing challenges: food security, climate change, and infrastructure development.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) provide a roadmap for this, allowing African nations to harness space for economic growth, environmental stewardship, and social welfare. By supporting the space industry, each citizen can directly contribute to the continent's ability to manage resources, reduce inequality, and build resilient communities. When space activities are guided by SDGs, they ensure that advancements **benefit all**, not just a privileged few, and foster inclusive growth aligned with Africa's collective values of unity, sustainability, and communal well-being.

The diagram below presents an overview of the problems and issues currently challenging the African space industry. [Issues that are considered wicked problems, are indicated with a 'WP'.]

LIMITED FUNDING AND INVESTMENT

WP

SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth

Underinvestment in space infrastructure limits job creation and economic development.

SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure

There is a need for sustainable industrial growth and innovation to drive advancements in space technology.

SPACE DEBRIS AND SUSTAINABLE USE OF OUTER SPACE

WP

SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production

Sustainable management of resources extends to space technologies, ensuring that space exploration does not contribute to space debris.

SDG 13: Climate Action

Space technologies can be part of the solution in monitoring and mitigating environmental challenges, including space debris.

LIMITED AWARENESS AND PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT

SDG 4: Quality Education

Increased educational efforts are required to build awareness of space science and its benefits.

SDG 16: Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions

Public participation and engagement in space policy-making processes are critical for inclusive decision-making.

LACK OF SKILLED WORKFORCE

SDG 4: Quality Education

The shortage of technical education and specialized training programs hinders capacity building in the space sector.

SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth

A lack of skilled personnel limits the potential for local employment in high-tech fields.

Wicked problems in the African space industry related to SDGs

SOVEREIGNTY AND EXTERNAL DEPENDENCE

WP

SDG 17: Partnerships for the Goals

While international collaboration is crucial, there needs to be a focus on fostering more self-reliance and reducing dependency on external actors.

FRAGMENTATION IN SPACE POLICY AND GOVERNANCE

WP

SDG 16: Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions

Developing strong institutions, laws, and policies at national and regional levels is essential for effective governance of the space industry.

ENVIRONMENTAL AND CLIMATE VULNERABILITY

WP

SDG 13: Climate Action

The space sector can contribute to climate monitoring and early warning systems, but environmental sustainability must be integrated into space initiatives.

SDG 15: Life on Land

Space technologies can support the preservation of terrestrial ecosystems by aiding environmental monitoring.

DIGITAL DIVIDE AND LIMITED ACCESS TO SPACE TECHNOLOGY

SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure

Access to space-based technologies can drive digital inclusion, particularly in remote areas.

SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities

Space-based technologies can help bridge inequality gaps, providing infrastructure for marginalised and underserved populations.

Diagram 1: Wicked problems in the African space industry and their relation to SDGs. (N van Rooyen, September 2024)

By addressing these challenges through targeted policies and initiatives aligned with the SDGs, Africa's space industry has the potential to not only contribute to the global space economy but also drive sustainable development within the continent.

Many of these issues fall into a 'wicked problem' category. A wicked problem refers to a problem that is difficult to define, has no clear solution, and is interconnected with other complex issues, often leading to unintended consequences when addressed.

Wicked problems tend to *resist clear solutions* because they are embedded in larger systems (for example, political, economic, and social systems), and efforts to address them often have unintended side effects.

Some issues like space debris or fragmented governance, for example, have a global scope, requiring multi-stakeholder approaches, making them even more difficult to resolve.

So, several issues from the above list would qualify as wicked problems - but others are complex and require careful navigation without necessarily fitting a "wicked" definition. The table below breaks down the characteristics classifying which issues might be wicked problems requiring alternative thinking in their resolution.

WP	WICKED PROBLEM	CLASSIFICATION
	Limited funding and investment	Funding limitations are deeply tied to broader economic, political, and governance issues. Attempts to address the problem may lead to unintended trade-offs, such as reliance on international partnerships that could limit national sovereignty or control over projects.
	Fragmentation in space policy and governance	Wicked in nature, this issue involves complex layers of national interests, regional coordination, and international relations. There are no straightforward solutions, as efforts to harmonise policies may face resistance from national governments or conflict with broader geopolitical goals.
	Environmental and climate vulnerability	Addressing climate vulnerability through space technology requires balancing various environmental, economic, and political considerations. Moreover, any solution may face opposition due to competing national priorities, funding constraints, or technological capacity, and may not be universally effective.
	Sovereignty and external dependence	This involves trade-offs between maintaining independence in space activities and the reliance on external actors for technology and resources. Achieving sovereignty in the space industry requires overcoming numerous political, economic, and technological hurdles, which are often interconnected with global dynamics.
	Space debris and sustainable use of outer space	The management of space debris is a wicked problem at a global level. No single nation can solve this issue alone, and the problem is compounded by the ever-increasing number of satellites being launched. Effective policies on debris management could conflict with the goals of other countries or commercial entities, making it difficult to find a globally acceptable solution.

By embracing the opportunities presented by space activities and applying sustainable development principles, policy efforts should aim to secure an African future grounded in ethics, legal practices, and environmental stewardship. This approach should link Africa's space industry to cultural identity and the global SDGs, appealing to a broad audience by emphasizing national pride, communal values, and the ethical care of both space and Earth.

What are the legal and policy challenges?

When tackling the complex issues related to the African space industry, it is crucial to address legal and policy challenges.

In tackling these legal and policy challenges, African countries can ensure that their space industry grows in a sustainable, secure, and beneficial manner.

A strong legal and regulatory framework serves as the foundation for tackling the complex issues tied to funding, governance, environmental responsibility, and the socioeconomic potential of space technology - all while safeguarding national and continental interests. The table below, lists an estimation of the current legal and policy challenges for African countries who have opted into pursuing space industry activities.

LEGAL and POLICY CHALLENGES for AFRICAN COUNTRIES PURSUING SPACE INDUSTRY ACTIVITIES

Fragmented policy frameworks

Many African countries lack comprehensive national space policies or legal frameworks, making regional coordination difficult. A unified African space policy is still emerging but arguably requires better governance structures.

Investment and funding

Robust programmes in satellite manufacturing, research, and human spaceflight are hampered by limited funding and investment into space activities. This includes immature legal mechanisms to attract investment in African space initiatives.

Private space activity regulation

Insufficient legal structures to regulate and support new private companies entering the African space sector. This includes issues of rights to intellectual property, licensing, and liability.

Space sovereignty and exploitation of resources

Although utilisation of space resources are priorities for African nations (for example, satellite data for agriculture or land issues), the protection of African interests in larger discussions around global space governance is still problematic, especially around resource-sharing of orbits and frequencies.

Skills and capacity development

Legal and policy frameworks must address education and building of capacity to support Africa's space ambitions.

There are existing global solutions that could possibly be adapted to resolve these challenges - such as capacity-building partnerships with organisations or private entities that could support knowledge-sharing and technology transfer.

Furthermore, adopting existing international space treaties (for example, the Moon Agreement, the Outer Space Treaty, etc.) and a host of SDG Treaties and Conventions could help serve as a foundational legal structure for space activities. These could then serve the basis for establishing regional cooperative governance models that help share resources, unify policies, and address gaps in regulation across various African nations.

In addition, African governments could develop strong 'access to market' frameworks through public-private partnerships to encourage private investment in space infrastructure (for example, satellite communication, Earth observation, etc).

Applying the Seven ‘Principles of International Law Relating to Sustainable Development’ to the African space industry

The *ILA 2002 New Delhi Declaration of Principles of International Law Relating to Sustainable Development* outlines seven principles aimed at promoting sustainability in global development. This holistic framework seeks to balance environmental protection with human development needs, ensuring fairness and long-term sustainability.

First, it emphasises the **integration and interrelationship** of environmental, social, and economic policies, ensuring these dimensions work together harmoniously.

The **sustainable use of natural resources** principle calls for responsible stewardship to prevent the depletion of resources for future generations.

The **equitable use of resources** ensures that all countries, especially developing ones, have fair access to global resources.

The declaration highlights the importance of **eradicating poverty**, recognising that sustainable development must prioritise the needs of the poor.

The **precautionary principle** suggests that precaution should be taken when actions may cause harm to the environment or human health, even if all scientific data is not available.

Public participation and access to information are also vital, ensuring transparency and that the public can engage in decision-making processes.

Lastly, **good governance** is a key principle, emphasising accountability, rule of law, and inclusive decision-making at all levels of governance to support sustainable development efforts.

Diagram: The seven Principles of International Law Relating to Sustainable Development' in the context of the space industry in Africa. (N. van Rooyen, Sept 2024)

Emerging Law specialties in the African space sector

The growth of the African space industry, its partnerships, sovereign priorities and continental coordination plans are giving rise to possibly new legal specialties. These are some fields that could support the compliance and relationship dynamics:

SPECIALITY	DESCRIPTION
Space Resource Law	Addressing the legalities around extracting resources from space (for example, asteroid mining) and ensuring African nations benefit from these opportunities.
Space Cybersecurity Law	As the reliance on satellite technology grows, laws regulating cybersecurity for space assets such as satellites and ground control stations are crucial.
Data Sovereignty and Privacy	Laws governing the ownership, access, and use of satellite data, particularly around geospatial data that affect national security, agriculture, and climate.
Environmental Space Law	Developing a legal framework to mitigate the environmental impacts of space activities (for example, debris management, sustainable satellite launching practices) and their potential Earth impacts.
Space Commerce and Liability	As private companies expand their role in space, regulations around space commerce in the areas of licensing, liability for accidents, and insurance will need to evolve.

Table: Possible emerging Law specialties in the African space sector.

The African space industry Value Chain, the SDGs, and Principles of Law

The space industry value chain includes all activities involved in developing, launching, operating, and utilising space technologies. In the African context, this value chain can essentially be broken down into the following elements:

- Research and development
- Manufacturing
- Launch service
- Ground operations
- Data analysis and application
- Policy and regulation

Each element of the space industry value chain contains various operations and activities that can be linked to specific sustainable development goals. Thus, there are several international principles of Law and global conventions and treaties aligned with these SDGs that could support the space industry value chain on a continental and national level. The framework below, attempts to approach multi-level integration of sustainable development principles supported by international treaties and SDG goals.

AFRICA'S SPACE INDUSTRY VALUE CHAIN ELEMENTS and ASSOCIATED SDGs

Diagram: The African Space Value Chain and associated SDGs (N van Rooyen, September 2024)

When considering the African space industry value chain, and related SDGs for each element, several governmental regulatory policies would typically need to be evaluated, or established, under existing treaties and conventions that underpin the SDG targets.

Moreover, embedding sustainability principles into all policies will support the long-term viability of space activities, considering ethical behaviours and the potential impact of these on other nations or regions, particularly around the exploitation of space resources.

The tables below, serve as recommendation for establishing a ‘SDG-Space Value Chain’ framework that can help ensure that the national space activity policies are in line with international obligations to ensure that industry activities are safe, sustainable, and compliant- a space-SDG ecosystem.

RECOMMENDED SDG ECOSYSTEM FOR AFRICA’S SPACE INDUSTRY

VALUE CHAIN ELEMENT	SUPPORTIVE SDG TREATIES	INTERNATIONAL LAW PRINCIPLES	GLOBAL CONVENTIONS	GOVERNMENT & REGULATORY POLICIES TO BE ADDRESSED
<p>Research and Development</p> <p>Includes activities related to innovation, scientific research, and the development of space technologies such as satellites, rockets, and related infrastructure.</p>	<p>UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC):</p> <p>Supports R&D for climate-related technologies (SDG 13).</p> <p>Paris Agreement (2015):</p> <p>Encourages innovation in technologies to combat climate change (SDG 13)</p>	<p>Implementing the Precautionary Principle by ensuring that new technologies undergo thorough environmental impact assessments.</p> <p>Aligning R&D with the Polluter Pays Principle by developing technologies that minimize environmental harm and internalize environmental costs</p>	<p>SDG 4 (Quality Education):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC, 1989). - Convention against Discrimination in Education (CADE, 1960). - UNESCO Convention against Discrimination in Education (1960). - World Declaration on Education for All (1990). - Sustainable Development Goal 4 (2015). <p>SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property (1883). - Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works (1886). - World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) treaties. - United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS, 1982). - Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015). - The World Trade Organization (WTO) agreements. - The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). - The Convention on International Civil Aviation (ICAO). - The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) conventions. 	<p>Intellectual Property (IP) Laws:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Protect innovations, patents, and trade secrets developed during R&D. ▪ Encourage innovation by providing legal protection for new technologies. <p>Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Regulations:</p> <p>Ensure that new technologies and research projects do not harm the environment.</p> <p>Funding and Grants Policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Government incentives and grants to support space-related R&D. ▪ Collaboration frameworks for public-private partnerships in R&D.
<p>SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure):</p> <p>R&D drives innovation and the development of infrastructure necessary for the space industry.</p>				
<p>SDG 4 (Quality Education):</p> <p>R&D activities promote education and skill development in science and technology.</p>				

VALUE CHAIN ELEMENT	SUPPORTIVE SDG TREATIES	INTERNATIONAL LAW PRINCIPLES	GLOBAL CONVENTIONS	GOVERNMENT & REGULATORY POLICIES TO BE ADDRESSED
<p>Manufacturing</p> <p>Involves the production of satellites, launch vehicles, ground equipment, and other space-related hardware.</p> <p>SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth):</p> <p>Manufacturing creates jobs and stimulates economic growth.</p> <p>SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production):</p> <p>Encourages sustainable production processes that minimize environmental impact.</p>	<p>Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants (2001): Ensures that manufacturing processes do not release harmful chemicals (SDG 12).</p> <p>Minamata Convention on Mercury (2013): Regulates the use of mercury in manufacturing, supporting safer production practices (SDG 12)</p>	<p>Adopting the Sustainable Use Principle by using raw materials responsibly and promoting recycling and reusability in manufacturing processes.</p> <p>Ensuring Intergenerational Equity by designing products with long-term environmental impacts in mind.</p>	<p>SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> International Labour Organization (ILO) conventions: <i>Forced Labour Convention (1930); Abolition of Forced Labour Convention (1957); Minimum Age Convention (1973); Worst Forms of Child Labour Convention (1999); Decent Work Agenda (2008).</i> United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD, 2006): promotes inclusive employment. International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families (ICRMW, 1990): safeguards migrant workers' rights. <p>SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption & Production):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC, 1992): addresses sustainable consumption and production patterns. Basel Convention on the Control of Transboundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and Their Disposal (1989): regulates waste management. Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs, 2001): aims to reduce harmful chemicals. Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES, 1973): regulates trade in endangered species. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) guidelines and agreements on sustainable consumption and production. The World Trade Organization (WTO) agreements on trade and environment. The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS, 1982) provisions on marine pollution. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) standards for sustainable management systems. 	<p>Standards and Certification Policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure that manufacturing processes and products meet international quality and safety standards. Certification of space components and systems to be used in space missions. <p>Health, Safety, and Environmental (HSE) Regulations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Address the safety of workers in the manufacturing sector. Environmental policies for waste management, emissions control, and sustainable resource use. <p>Export Control and Trade Regulations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Control the export of sensitive technologies and materials used in space manufacturing. Compliance with international arms control treaties, as space technologies can have dual-use implications.

VALUE CHAIN ELEMENT	SUPPORTIVE SDG TREATIES	INTERNATIONAL LAW PRINCIPLES	GLOBAL CONVENTIONS	GOVERNMENT & REGULATORY POLICIES TO BE ADDRESSED
<p>Launch Services</p> <p>This includes the preparation and execution of satellite launches, whether through indigenous launch capabilities or international partnerships.</p> <p>SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure):</p> <p>Launch services are critical for establishing and maintaining space infrastructure.</p> <p>SDG 13 (Climate Action):</p> <p>Launch services contribute to the deployment of satellites for climate monitoring.</p>	<p>Outer Space Treaty (1967): Governs the peaceful exploration of space, ensuring that launch activities do not contribute to militarization (SDG 16).</p> <p>Montreal Protocol (1987): While primarily focused on ozone depletion, it indirectly impacts launch services by regulating substances that could be released into the atmosphere (SDG 13)</p>	<p>Implementing the Principle of Integration by considering environmental and social impacts alongside economic benefits in launch decisions.</p> <p>Applying the Precautionary Principle by assessing and mitigating the environmental risks associated with launches.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC, 1992): sets global framework for addressing climate change. ▪ Paris Agreement (2015): aims to limit global warming to well below 2°C and pursue efforts to limit it to 1.5°C. ▪ Kyoto Protocol (1997): sets binding emissions targets for developed countries. ▪ Vienna Convention for the Protection of the Ozone Layer (1985): addresses ozone-depleting substances. ▪ Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer (1987): regulates ozone-depleting substances. ▪ United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD, 1994): addresses land degradation and desertification. ▪ Convention on International Civil Aviation (ICAO, 1944): sets standards for reducing aviation emissions. ▪ International Maritime Organization (IMO) conventions: regulate emissions from shipping. ▪ The World Meteorological Organization (WMO) conventions on weather and climate. ▪ The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS, 1982) provisions on ocean acidification. ▪ The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD, 1992) provisions on ecosystem resilience. ▪ The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) standards for climate change mitigation and adaptation. 	<p>Space Launch Licensing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Licensing policies for launching satellites and other space objects. ▪ Regulations to ensure the safety of launch operations and compliance with international space treaties, such as the Outer Space Treaty. <p>Environmental Regulations:</p> <p>Policies addressing the environmental impact of launches, including emissions and potential pollution from launch sites.</p> <p>Airspace and Maritime Coordination:</p> <p>Policies for coordinating with civil aviation authorities and maritime agencies to secure airspace and waters during launches.</p> <p>Debris Mitigation Guidelines:</p> <p>Regulations aligned with international standards (e.g., UN Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines) to minimize space debris from launches.</p>

VALUE CHAIN ELEMENT	SUPPORTIVE SDG TREATIES	INTERNATIONAL LAW PRINCIPLES	GLOBAL CONVENTIONS	GOVERNMENT & REGULATORY POLICIES TO BE ADDRESSED
<p>Ground Operations</p> <p>Involves managing satellite operations, data reception, and the maintenance of ground control stations.</p> <p>SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities):</p> <p>Ground operations provide critical services for urban planning and disaster management.</p> <p>SDG 13 (Climate Action):</p> <p>Supports monitoring and responding to climate change through satellite data.</p>	<p>Kyoto Protocol (1997):</p> <p>Supports ground operations through mechanisms that monitor greenhouse gas emissions (SDG 13).</p> <p>Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015):</p> <p>Encourages the use of satellite data for disaster preparedness and response (SDG 11)</p>	<p>Utilizing the Principle of Public Participation to involve local communities in decisions related to ground stations and operations.</p> <p>Enforcing the Polluter Pays Principle by managing the environmental impact of ground operations, such as electronic waste from satellite control equipment.</p>	<p>SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> United Nations Habitat Agenda (1996): sets global framework for sustainable urban development. New Urban Agenda (2016): aims to promote sustainable urbanization. Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD, 2006): promotes inclusive and accessible urban planning. UNESCO World Heritage Convention (1972): protects cultural and natural heritage in urban areas. International Guidelines on Urban and Territorial Planning (2015): provides framework for sustainable urban planning. UN-Habitat's Sustainable Urban Development Network (SUD-Net): promotes knowledge sharing and cooperation. The Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015): aims to reduce disaster risk in urban areas. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) standards for sustainable cities and communities. <p>SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines on urban health and air quality. The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) guidelines on sustainable urban environment. The International Labour Organization (ILO) conventions on urban employment and decent work. The World Bank's Urban and Disaster Risk Management department guidelines. 	<p>Telecommunications and Spectrum Management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies governing the allocation and use of radio frequencies for satellite communication. Compliance with the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) regulations. <p>Infrastructure Development Policies:</p> <p>Guidelines for building and maintaining ground stations, including land use and environmental impact assessments.</p> <p>Data Privacy and Security Regulations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure the security of data transmitted between space assets and ground stations. Protect sensitive information and adhere to privacy laws. <p>Emergency Response and Disaster Management:</p> <p>Policies ensuring that ground operations can support disaster response efforts through satellite data.</p>

VALUE CHAIN ELEMENT	SUPPORTIVE SDG TREATIES	INTERNATIONAL LAW PRINCIPLES	GLOBAL CONVENTIONS	GOVERNMENT & REGULATORY POLICIES TO BE ADDRESSED
<p>Data Analysis and Application</p> <p>Includes processing, analysing, and applying satellite data for various purposes (weather forecasting, environmental monitoring, agriculture, and communication).</p> <p>SDG 2 (Zero Hunger):</p> <p>Satellite data supports agricultural planning and food security.</p> <p>SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being):</p> <p>Data applications can improve healthcare delivery through telemedicine and monitoring of environmental health factors.</p>	<p>Convention on Biological Diversity (1992):</p> <p>Promotes the use of satellite data for biodiversity conservation (SDG 15).</p> <p>International Health Regulations (2005):</p> <p>Utilize satellite data for monitoring health-related events (SDG 3)</p>	<p>Ensuring Access to Information by making satellite data publicly available for environmental monitoring and public health purposes.</p> <p>Promoting Sustainable Development by using data to support SDGs like zero hunger (SDG 2) and climate action (SDG 13)</p>	<p>SDG 2 (Zero Hunger):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Right to Food guidelines (2004): interprets the right to food as a human right. International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (2001): conserves crop diversity. Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES, 1973): regulates trade in endangered species. Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) guidelines on sustainable agriculture. World Trade Organization (WTO) agreements on agriculture and trade. United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD, 1994): addresses land degradation. International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) conventions on rural development. <p>SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> World Health Organization (WHO) Constitution (1946): sets global health goals. International Health Regulations (2005): coordinates global health responses. United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD, 2006): promotes inclusive healthcare. Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW, 1979): addresses women's health. United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC, 1989): addresses children's health. WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (2003): regulates tobacco use. International Labour Organization (ILO) conventions on occupational health and safety. The World Food Programme (WFP) guidelines on food security. The United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) guidelines on child health and nutrition. The Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS) guidelines on HIV/AIDS response. The Global Health Security Agreement (2007) on pandemic preparedness. 	<p>Data Protection and Privacy Laws:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulations to protect the privacy of individuals whose data might be collected or analyzed. Guidelines on the ethical use of satellite data, especially in sensitive areas such as surveillance. <p>Open Data and Sharing Policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote the sharing of satellite data for public good, such as environmental monitoring and disaster management. Frameworks for collaboration between government, academia, and private sector entities. <p>Sector-Specific Regulations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies addressing the use of satellite data in agriculture, healthcare, urban planning, etc. Compliance with international standards for data handling and processing.

VALUE CHAIN ELEMENT	SUPPORTIVE SDG TREATIES	INTERNATIONAL LAW PRINCIPLES	GLOBAL CONVENTIONS	GOVERNMENT & REGULATORY POLICIES TO BE ADDRESSED
<p>Policy and Regulation</p> <p>Encompasses the governance, legal frameworks, and international cooperation necessary for space activities.</p>	<p>Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (1969):</p> <p>Ensures that international agreements related to space are interpreted and applied consistently (SDG 16).</p> <p>UN Declaration on International Cooperation in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space for the Benefit and in the Interest of All States (1996):</p> <p>Promotes international cooperation in space activities (SDG 17)</p>	<p>Ensuring Good Governance by transparently creating and enforcing regulations that support sustainable development in the space industry.</p> <p>Implementing Common but Differentiated Responsibilities by supporting developing countries in accessing space technologies and data</p>	<p>SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> United Nations Charter (1945): establishes the UN and promotes peace and security. Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948): sets global human rights standards. International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (1966): protects civil and political rights. Convention against Corruption (2003): combats corruption. Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (2000): addresses organized crime. Geneva Conventions (1949) and Additional Protocols (1977, 2005): regulate humanitarian law. United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS, 1982): establishes maritime law and dispute resolution. <p>SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC, 1992): promotes global climate cooperation. World Trade Organization (WTO) agreements: facilitate international trade and cooperation. Paris Agreement (2015): strengthens global climate cooperation. Addis Ababa Action Agenda (2015): promotes financing for development. Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015): enhances disaster risk reduction cooperation. United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD, 1994): addresses land degradation and desertification. International Organization for Standardization (ISO) standards: promote global cooperation and standardization. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) guidelines on governance and institutional development. The World Bank's guidelines on good governance and anti-corruption. The International Labour Organization (ILO) conventions on labor rights and social dialogue. The United Nations Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) guidelines on partnerships and cooperation. 	<p>National Space Policy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A comprehensive policy outlining the government's vision, objectives, and strategy for space activities. Alignment with international space law and treaties, such as the Outer Space Treaty, Moon Agreement, and others. <p>International Cooperation and Treaties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies promoting collaboration with other countries and participation in international space organizations, such as the African Space Agency (AfSA). Compliance with treaties like the Outer Space Treaty, Registration Convention, and Liability Convention. <p>Public Engagement and Education Policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote public awareness and education about space activities. Encourage STEM education and capacity building to support the growth of the space industry.
<p>SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions):</p> <p>Effective policies ensure that space activities are governed by the rule of law and promote peaceful uses of space.</p> <p>SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals):</p> <p>International cooperation and partnerships are essential for the development of space activities in Africa.</p>				

Why should it matter?

Space activities should be governed by ethical and legal principles that respect the planet and its people, ensuring that technological progress does not come at the cost of indigenous rights or environmental degradation.

African nations have an opportunity to lead by example in integrating these principles with their own cultural values.

The African Union's focus on cooperation and shared benefits aligns with global ethical standards while respecting the continent's history of interconnected communities. By incorporating indigenous knowledge systems into space practices, Africa can set a precedent for ethical space exploration that prioritises environmental protection, justice, and respect for ancestral lands.

The IMPORTANCE of ALIGNING SPACE POLICY with SDG PRINCIPLES of LAW and SOVEREIGN IDENTITY

Creating a stable and predictable environment	A well-defined legal and policy framework provides stability and predictability, which is essential for attracting investment, both domestically and internationally. Clear regulations encourage private sector engagement, international partnerships, and technological transfers that can accelerate the development of the African space industry.	For example: If space industry laws are ambiguous or non-existent, private companies and international partners may hesitate to invest or collaborate, fearing legal risks or uncertainties.
Strengthening national sovereignty and reducing external dependence	Countries need legal mechanisms to protect their space assets, data sovereignty, and the management of national resources in space. Without appropriate laws and policies, external actors could dominate the African space market, making countries overly reliant on foreign technology, expertise, and infrastructure.	For example: By having comprehensive legal frameworks, African nations can negotiate international partnerships from a position of strength, ensuring fair agreements that prioritize national interests.
Ensuring ethical and sustainable use of space	Legal and policy frameworks are needed to guide the ethical use of space, preventing exploitation, overcrowding, and irresponsible behaviour that leads to issues like space debris. African countries must be part of global discussions on space governance to ensure their interests are protected while also contributing to the sustainable management of space.	For example: Policies can dictate how countries should handle the environmental impact of their space activities and mitigate risks such as satellite collisions or space debris.
Building continental and regional cooperation	Collaboration among African nations is essential for overcoming the fragmentation of the space sector on the continent. By creating shared legal frameworks, African countries can pool resources, share data, and coordinate their efforts to achieve collective goals. Regional cooperation can also help address cross-border issues such as satellite coverage and data sharing.	For example: The African Space Policy, endorsed by the African Union, aims to coordinate national efforts into a cohesive regional strategy. Legal alignment across borders can enhance this initiative and make it more effective.
Protecting against geopolitical risks	As the space industry grows, so does its geopolitical significance. African countries need legal frameworks to protect themselves from potential conflicts related to space assets and ensure that they are not drawn into geopolitical tensions among space-faring nations. These frameworks can also protect national interests in the event of space-based disputes.	For example: Without a strong legal stance, African countries may find themselves vulnerable in situations where foreign satellites pass over their territories or extract space-based data without consent.

Why should it matter? *continued*

The importance of aligning space policy with SDG principles of law and sovereign identity, *continued*

Maximising the socioeconomic benefits of space	Legal and policy frameworks can help African countries ensure that the space industry contributes to broader development goals, such as poverty reduction, healthcare, education, and agriculture. They can create policies that direct space technologies toward addressing socioeconomic needs, such as satellite-based internet access in rural areas or earth observation for monitoring agriculture.	For example: National space policies can mandate that space technology investments are linked to achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), ensuring that space technology benefits society.
Promoting innovation and capacity building	Well-structured policies are essential for creating incentives for innovation, research, and development in space technologies. Legal frameworks that support intellectual property protection, local manufacturing, and the development of local talent can boost Africa's ability to compete in the global space economy.	For example: Space policies that support educational initiatives, research institutions, and public-private partnerships can lead to a flourishing ecosystem where local innovation thrives.
Integrating with global space law	The space industry is governed by international treaties and agreements, such as the Outer Space Treaty, which ensure that space is used for peaceful purposes and benefit all of humanity. African countries need to align their national policies with global standards to participate in international space activities, avoid conflicts, and benefit from global cooperation.	For example: African nations can enhance their role in global space governance by participating in international regulatory bodies, contributing to global discussions, and ensuring compliance with international treaties.
Mitigating legal and regulatory barriers	Without clear legal and regulatory frameworks, space industry participants may face barriers such as burdensome bureaucracy, corruption, or inconsistencies in how laws are applied. Addressing these challenges ensures a smoother, more efficient process for stakeholders in the space industry, encouraging faster development.	For example: Countries with clear space policies are better able to facilitate the licensing of satellites, regulation of launch activities, and legal dispute resolution.

Supporting space activities, therefore, is not just about technological advancement but about contributing to a future where space exploration is carried out with responsibility and integrity, ensuring that Africa's voice and values are heard on the global stage.

*Historically, Africa has been underrepresented in global space exploration - yet space presents a unique opportunity for African countries to reclaim their place in the global narrative, developing technologies and policies that reflect their cultural values, aspirations, and histories. By contributing to space activities, citizens not only participate in scientific progress but also in the creation of an **African Space Identity** that celebrates the continent's rich cultural heritage and indigenous knowledge.*